

Preparation and photocatalytic activity of visible-light-driven mesoporous titania photocatalyst co-doped with B and S

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Abstract : In order to improve the photocatalytic performance of mesoporous titania (MTiO₂) under visible light, a boron and sulfur co-doped MTiO₂ photocatalyst was prepared by template method using boric acid triethyl ester, thiourea and tetrabutyl titanate (Ti(OC₄H₉)₄) as precursors and Pluronic P123 as template. The microstructure of as-prepared photocatalyst was characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and N₂ adsorption-desorption measurements. The microcrystal of the co-doped photocatalyst consisted of anatase phase and was approximately present in the form of spherical particle. The particle size was in correlation with the calcination temperature. The photocatalytic performance was studied by photodegradation methyl blue (MB) in water under visible light irradiation. The calcination temperature and the doping content influenced the photoactivity. The effect of boron and sulfur co-doping played an important role in improving the photocatalytic activity.

Keywords : Visible light photocatalysis, mesoporous titania, boron, sulfur, co-doping.

Introduction

Titania (TiO₂) is a semiconductor photocatalyst widely used in sensors^{1,2}, solar cells³, lithium-ion cells⁴ and many others. It is a promising photocatalyst for remediation of organic pollutants in air⁵⁻⁷ and water⁸⁻¹¹. Compared with TiO₂, mesoporous TiO₂, which displays better photocatalytic activity because of its high specific surface area and uniform pore diameter, has therefore received much interest in photocatalysis^{12,13}. However, mesoporous TiO₂ can be activated only by ultraviolet (UV) light because of its high energy band gap (*ca.* 3.0 eV for rutile and 3.2 eV for anatase). So it is necessary to develop the novel visible-light-driven photocatalyst. In addition, for practical application to decompose indoor organic pollutants, it is necessary to extend the photoabsorption of mesoporous titania into visible light region. An efficient process that shifts the optical response of active mesoporous TiO₂ from the UV to the visible spectral range and to longer wavelength is doping elements¹⁴⁻¹⁶. In the present, the investigations about doping elements focused mostly on transition metal ions doping¹⁷⁻¹⁹ and rare earth metal doping^{20,21}. However, metal doping has several drawbacks such as thermal instability and the metal centers act as electron

traps, which reduces the photocatalytic efficiency. Asahi *et al.*²² first reported the N-doped titania photocatalyst exhibiting photoabsorption at wavelengths longer than 400 nm and photocatalytic activity under visible light. From there on, some researchers paid much attention to the modification of titania by incorporating nonmetals, such as phosphorus²³, sulfur²⁴, fluorine²⁵, boron²⁶ and carbon²⁷. Furthermore, there were also a few reports on titania photocatalysts co-doped by two kinds of nonmetals^{28,29}. Obviously, doping with these nonmetals can decrease the band gap and result in the response to the visible light of photocatalysts. However, few studies reported the effects of boron and sulfur co-doping and heat treatment on photocatalytic activity and microstructures of mesoporous titania powders. In the present paper, we used Pluronic P123 as template, and tetrabutyl titanate, boric acid triethyl ester and thiourea as the sources of titanium, boron and sulfur to prepare mesoporous titania photocatalyst co-doped with B and S. Then, we focused on the characterization of the as-prepared titania samples and the investigation of the effects of heat treatment temperature on the structure, the crystallinity, and the photocatalytic activity of co-doped mesoporous TiO₂.

Experimental

Photocatalyst preparation :

In a typical synthesis, 0.01 mol (3.4 g) of tetrabutyl-titanate ($\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_4\text{H}_9)_4$, analytic grade, Shanghai Xingta Co. Ltd., China) was added to a solution containing 1.0 g of Pluronic P123 ($\text{EO}_{20}\text{PO}_{70}\text{EO}_{20}$, Aldrich Chemical Co., Milwaukee, WI) and 8.0 mL of anhydrous ethanol to obtain solution A. A certain amount of boric acid triethyl ester, and thiourea was dissolved in the mixture of 2.0 mL of deionized water, 1.5 mL of glacial acetic acid, and 8.0 mL of anhydrous ethanol at room temperature to gain solution B.

The solution A was added dropwise into the solution B within 60 min by separating funnel while keeping the reaction mixture vigorously magnetically stirred. The resulting white slurry was stirred continuously for 1 h, aged for 48 h at room temperature, and dried for 10 h at 100 °C under reduced pressure to gain the xerogel. The resultant xerogel was crushed to obtain fine powder and further calcined at desired temperature for 2 h to remove the residual organic compounds resulting from the hydrolysis of the $\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_4\text{H}_9)_4$ and the surfactant to prepare the co-doped photocatalyst. The calcined samples were labeled as $\text{B}_x\text{S}_y\text{-MTiO}_2\text{-t}$, where x and y corresponded to the initial mole ratios of B to Ti and S to Ti, respectively, and t was the corresponding temperature of calcinations (°C).

Characterization :

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) micro-images of pure MTiO_2 and $\text{B}_{0.01}\text{S}_{0.02}\text{-MTiO}_2\text{-400}$ were obtained on a Philips XL-30 (25 kV, LaB6 filament) scanning electron microscope. Wide-angle X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) patterns of all samples were obtained at room temperature with a Rigaku D/max-r B X-ray diffractometer using $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation which operated at 45 kV and 40 mA. Information about specific surface area and pore volume of catalysts was calculated using the BET method³⁰ from nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms measured at 77 K with a Micromeritics 2000 instrument (ASAP 2000, Micromeritics, USA).

Measurement of photocatalytic efficiency :

The photocatalytic activity of the prepared catalysts under visible light was estimated by measuring the degradation rate of MB ($20 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) in an aqueous solution. Experiments were carried out using a magnetically stirred quartz reactor and a 150 W metal halide lamp as the light source at ambient temperature of about 20 °C. To limit

the irradiation wavelength, the light beam was passed through a 410 nm cut filter (L41) to assure cut-off wavelengths shorter than 410 nm. Sixty-minute adsorption time in dark condition was allowed before the start of photoreactions. Then, samples of the suspension were withdrawn after a definite time interval and filtered through 0.45 μm filter paper. The filtrates were analyzed for residual MB concentration using a UV-vis spectrophotometer (UV762, Shanghai Analysis Co.). All the experiments were triplicate. The results presented were the mean values with a total error of less than 5%.

Results and discussion

Characterization :

Fig. 1 shows the SEM images of the pure MTiO_2 and $\text{B}_{0.01}\text{S}_{0.02}\text{-MTiO}_2\text{-400}$. It indicated that particles of pure MTiO_2 congregated together so densely that few gaps existed between the pores. In contrast, the particles of co-doped sample congregated loosely. It could be observed that samples were approximately present in the

Fig. 1. SEM images of samples (a) $\text{MTiO}_2\text{-400}$, (b) $\text{B}_{0.01}\text{S}_{0.02}\text{-MTiO}_2\text{-400}$.

form of spherical particle with the average size around 10 nm. The result was in accordance with the values determined by XRD (10–12 nm).

The XRD patterns of prepared samples calcined at different temperatures were shown in Fig. 2. It could be observed that all B and S co-doped MTiO_2 powders were present in the anatase phases regardless of the calcination temperature and that there was no evident difference be-

Fig. 2. XRD patterns of samples.

tween anatase MTiO_2 and B, S co-doped MTiO_2 . The diffraction peaks at 25.38, 37.80, 48.05, 55.07 and 70.25° are consistent with the (101), (004), (200), (105) and (220) peaks of anatase titania. The XRD results suggested that the B and S co-doping has little influence on the nature of crystal formation. It could be also seen that the peak intensities of anatase increased and the width of the (101) plane diffraction peak of anatase (25.38°) became narrower. It indicated that the average particle size increased with the increase of the calcination temperature. The physical properties determined from XRD data of the samples were listed in Table 1. The information about specific surface area, pore volume and BET surface area of the as-prepared catalysts were summarized in Table 2. It could be seen that the average particle sizes of the as-prepared samples were around 10–12 nm. Compared with pure MTiO_2 ($a = b = 0.3774$ nm and $c = 0.9517$ nm),

Table 1. XRD analysis result of samples

Sample	Crystallite size (nm)	Lattice parameters		
		a (nm)	c (nm)	V (nm ³)
MTiO_2 -400	11.5	0.3774	0.9517	0.1356
$\text{B}_{0.01}\text{S}_{0.02}\text{-MTiO}_2$ -300	10.5	0.3783	0.9512	0.1361
$\text{B}_{0.01}\text{S}_{0.02}\text{-MTiO}_2$ -400	10.9	0.3769	0.9495	0.1349
$\text{B}_{0.01}\text{S}_{0.02}\text{-MTiO}_2$ -500	11.2	0.3762	0.9481	0.1342

Table 2. Summary of the physicochemical properties of doped mesoporous TiO_2

Sample	S_{BET} (m ² g ⁻¹)	Total pore volume (cm ³ g ⁻¹)	Average pore diameter (nm)
MTiO_2 -400	151.8	0.327	11.3
$\text{B}_{0.01}\text{S}_{0.02}\text{-MTiO}_2$ -300	143.3	0.336	10.6
$\text{B}_{0.01}\text{S}_{0.02}\text{-MTiO}_2$ -400	159.2	0.352	9.9
$\text{B}_{0.01}\text{S}_{0.02}\text{-MTiO}_2$ -500	141.4	0.328	9.4

it was clear that the lattice parameters a and b of the co-doped samples remained almost unvaried while the c parameters decreased. This demonstrated that the crystal lattices of the as-prepared samples were locally distorted by doping.

Photocatalytic activity :

Photocatalytic activity of B and S co-doped mesopore titania samples was estimated by measuring the degradation rate of MB (20 mg·L⁻¹) in the presence of visible light irradiation without concerning the degradation intermediates in detail. Pure mesopore titania synthesized by the same method without any dopant was used as the reference system. It was found that MB concentration remained stable after 1 h of stirring without illumination in the presence of obtained samples. Fig. 3 shows the results of MB degradation with irradiation time under visible light irradiation in the presence of as-prepared photocatalysts. It could be observed that all as-prepared samples exhibited higher photocatalytic activity than pure MTiO_2 under visible light. It could be also seen that the calcination temperature and the co-doped content of the as-prepared samples had an effect on the degradation ratios. Among the samples, the best performance was attributed to $\text{B}_{0.01}\text{S}_{0.02}\text{-MTiO}_2$ -400. It could be calculated that the photocatalytic performance of $\text{B}_{0.01}\text{S}_{0.02}\text{-MTiO}_2$ -400 was almost twice times higher than that of pure MTiO_2 for degradation of MB under visible light. Obviously, the photocatalytic activity of B and S co-doped MTiO_2 under visible light demonstrated that B, S co-doping effect was

Fig. 3. Degradation curves of MB with visible light irradiation time.

outstanding. This was ascribed to the cooperative effects of B and S co-doping. According to the previous report³¹, many factors influenced the photoactivity of photocatalyst and these factors were closely related to each other. Therefore, it was not difficult to understand that the highest photocatalytic performance was achieved at a particular calcination temperature and doping content.

Among the samples, the B_{0.01}S_{0.02}-MTiO₂-400 showed the best photocatalytic performance. This result should be due to the positive effect of the introduction of B and S on the photocatalytic activity because the co-doping not only increased the surface area of mesoporous titania (Table 2) but also extended its photoabsorption to visible light region. The surface area is one of the key factors to control the photocatalytic activity of a photocatalyst. The larger the surface area is, the higher the photocatalytic activity is. Furthermore, the photoabsorption characters greatly affect the photocatalytic activity of a photocatalyst, since the numbers of absorbed photons directly depend on the absorption property of the photocatalyst. B_{0.01}S_{0.02}-MTiO₂-400 exhibited the highest photocatalytic activity under visible light irradiation could be explained by the competition and balance of the two factors above.

Conclusions

A composite photocatalyst of B and S co-doped mesoporous titania was successfully prepared by template method using boric acid triethyl ester, thiourea and

Ti(OC₄H₉)₄ as precursors and Pluronic P123 as template. The photocatalyst thus prepared was applied to degrade model contaminated water of MB. The as-prepared photocatalyst only contained anatase phase. The doping content and the calcination temperature had an effect on the photocatalytic activity of the photocatalyst. The synergistic effect of B and S co-doping was responsible for improving the photocatalytic performance. The factors such as surface area, co-doping content and photoabsorption affect the photocatalytic activity of B and S co-doped mesoporous titania.

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Yao *et al.* : Preparation and photocatalytic activity of visible-light-driven mesoporous *etc.*

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